

MULTIMINER – MULTI-SOURCE AND MULTI-SCALE EARTH OBSERVATION AND NOVEL MACHINE LEARNING METHODS FOR MINERAL EXPLORATION AND MINE SITE MONITORING

by

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The Multi-source and Multi-scale Earth observation and Novel Machine Learning Methods for Mineral Exploration and Mine Site Monitoring (MultiMiner) project is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) project funded from the Horizon Europe programme in years 2023–2036. The goal of the project is to develop novel data processing algorithms for cost-effective utilisation of Earth Observation (EO) technologies for mineral exploration and mine site monitoring (Fig. 1). The purpose is to further unlock the potential of EO data, including Copernicus, commercial satellites, upcoming missions, airborne and low altitude as well as *in situ* data. Solutions are created for all stages of the mining life cycle including mineral exploration, operational, closure and post-closure stages. The core idea of the MultiMiner project is to create innovative machine learning solutions which do not require any or only little *in situ* reference data. The project focuses on new EO based exploration technologies for critical raw materials (CRM) to increase the probability of finding new sources within EU thereby strengthening the EU autonomy in the area of raw materials. MultiMiner EO based exploration solutions have extremely low environmental impact, and are thus socially acceptable, economically efficient and improve safety. The project's solutions for mine site monitoring increase the transparency of mining operations as environmental impacts can be detected as early as possible and digital information of the currently unexploitable raw materials can be stored for future generations. The applicability of the developed algorithms is demonstrated in five European test sites (Fig. 2). The core scientific work in the project is divided into three work packages where the first two develop algorithms for mineral exploration and mine site monitoring, and the third one demonstrates their applicability and accuracy in real mining and exploration environments of critical and strategic raw materials.

Work package 2, **Multi-source and multi-scale mineral prospectivity EO mapping**, develops scalable and automated approaches for mineral exploration based on multi-source EO data and sparse *in situ* data. The focus is on mineral deposits hosting CRMs. Firstly, a novel mineral mapping algorithm performing automatic spectral feature extraction from a comprehensive mineral spectral library is developed. This algorithm will significantly improve accuracy and time-efficiency of direct mineral identification of CRMs and other raw materials based on EO data. Secondly, we implement workflows for multi-scale EO data interpretation, to produce value adding mineral maps for local to regional scale exploration. Thirdly, a mineral prospectivity wizard, facilitating multi-scale mineral mapping and automatic interpretation for non-experts, is coded and tested.

Fig. 1. MultiMiner project takes advantage of recent space- and airborne EO technologies and harnesses them for the use of mining industry by creating efficient unsupervised and weakly-supervised data analysis algorithms which require limited *in situ* data.

In work package 3, **Timely mine site monitoring**, novel EO data analysis methods are designed and developed to make use of the scarcely available *in situ* data for timely mine site monitoring. The larger goal is to reduce both disruptions to mining activities and environmental impacts. The objectives are 1) to develop a novel generic mine site monitoring algorithm, capable of combining multi-source EO data at various temporal, spatial and spectral resolutions, and requiring only a limited amount of *in situ* data, 2) to adapt and fine tune the generic algorithm to automatically monitor impacts to the environment, including water quality, acid mine drainage, dust and revegetation, and 3) to develop an integrated 3D tailings storage facility monitoring method, capable of jointly monitoring tailings composition and volume, as well as ground stability of tailings dams and open pit walls.

Finally, work package 4, **Site demonstrations**, showcases the novel exploration and monitoring methods developed in work packages 2 and 3. The demonstrations are conducted in four active mining sites, namely Hochfilzen, Austria (RHI Magnesita) and Olympias and Stratoni, Greece (Hellas Gold) and Ihalainen, Finland

The MultiMiner project follows the open access policy for algorithms, data, their metadata and publications, whenever possible. New unsupervised easy-to-use tools to conduct EO-based mineral exploration and mine site monitoring are made available for further exploitation and development through Github. In the long run the project's solutions for EO-based exploration are expected to lead to potential discoveries of new CRM deposits. In addition, mine site monitoring solutions are expected to increase the transparency of mining operations enabling environmental impacts to be detected as early as possible, and also lead to better mining safety. In that respect, MultiMiner will engage actively with the general public and policy makers to raise the awareness about the project and its objectives, and share its innovative methods with European stakeholders to stimulate further research and developments, and ensure their exploitation by end-users (mining industry, governmental and non-governmental organisations, scientific community, local authorities, etc.).

MultiMiner is a pan-European consortium consisting of 12 partners and 1 associated partner from research institutes, academia, consulting businesses and mining industry with interdisciplinary backgrounds in geology, remote sensing and machine learning (Fig. 2). The members come from six EU member states which represent mining regions across Europe with diverse geology with evident potential for various types of CRM resources. The project is led by Geological Survey of Finland, GTK. For further information follow the project on the project webpage at www.multiminer.eu and at social media channels.